

STUDIES OF THE INFLUENCE OF 'AGEING' UNDER AN OZONISER DISCHARGE ON THE JOSHI EFFECT IN HIGH PRESSURE CHLORINE

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Influence of 'ageing' on the Joshi effect in high pressure chlorine has been studied. In a freshly prepared ozoniser, the effect varied appreciably with the time of exposure to discharge. This has been attributed, in part, to an interaction between the (electrode) wall material and the activated gas under the discharge, leading to the formation of a boundary layer on the electrodes. The influence of light frequency was investigated on the Joshi effect, produced at potentials 1 to 4 kV, and also in respect of its variation under 'ageing.' It was found that the effect Δi and % Δi varied *frequencywise*, viz., white > blue > green > red. The effect under unfiltered white was found to be less than the additive effect due to the filtered components, viz., blue, green and red; this difference decreased with the exciting potential. The influence of 'ageing' leading to the enhancement of the effect, Δi , followed the order: red > green > blue > white. Both the net and the relative effect increase with temperature in high pressure chlorine. Under constant mass conditions the rise of temperature brings about a rise in the gas pressure, which makes for an increase in Δi . An enhanced (due to heating) chemical action between the excited gas and the wall material also favours Δi , by abstracting from the extra high gas pressure, which ordinarily inhibits the effect Δi .

The marked dependence of the magnitude of the above phenomenon, Δi , an instantaneous and reversible photo-diminution of the discharge current, i , on factors such as the gas pressure, temperature, the net surface exposed to discharge, etc., is known (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, Sec. III, p. 51). This effect, Δi , tends to increase with pressure up to a limit (about 93 % with but ordinary light at about 460 mm. pressure) and decrease thereafter (Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1944, **154**, 343). It was also found over a wide range of conditions that the Joshi effect decreased with temperature (Deo and Padmanabhulu, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1944, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, *Abst.* No. 36; Deo and Urs, *ibid.*, 1945, *Phys. Sec.*, *Abst.* No. 16). A limitation of this deduction has now been observed in the use of gas pressure, much larger than those employed by earlier workers. The marked influence of ageing under discharge, on the magnitude and even sign of the above phenomenon, was observed by Joshi (*loc. cit.*), and is implicit in Joshi's recent theory thereof (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, *Abst.* No. 26; *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, **16**, 19). This 'ageing' factor has now been investigated in some detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

The arrangement of the apparatus and the electrical circuit are shown in Fig. 1. Alternating potentials of 500 cycles frequency, obtained from a rotary converter and stepped up with a transformer, were applied to a Siemens' glass ozoniser containing chlorine, purified over liquid air, at 540 mm. pressure. The exciting potential was varied from 1 to 4 kV. In each series, the discharge current was observed in dark (i_0), and under irradiation (i_1) from a 220 volt, 200 watt incandescent (glass) bulb; a low

resistance Cambridge vacuo-junction along with a galvanometer was employed as a current detector. The values of i_b and i_L are given in arbitrary units of the galvanometer scale deflections. The system was enclosed in an electrical heater in the form of a rectangular box with asbestos walls, whose temperature could be varied in the range of 25° to 80° by regulation of the heating current. Two series of experiments were carried out, one with ozoniser A, and the other with ozoniser B, filled with purified chlorine at 540 mm. pressure.

FIG. 1

The variation of Joshi effect with 'ageing' under discharge in a fresh ozoniser A, at 2.67 kV (25°) was studied, and the results are given in Table I. Table II shows the influence of exciting potential (kV) and light frequency on Joshi effect in ozoniser A, 'aged' under discharge. The influence of light frequency on Joshi effect during ageing of the further aged ozoniser A, was also investigated and the results are tabulated in Table III. The comparative influence of temperature and exciting potential (kV) on the Joshi effect in a long aged ozoniser A, and fresh one B, was studied and the results are recorded in Table IV. The effective frequency of irradiation was varied by the use of appropriate light filters.

TABLE I

Variation of the Joshi-effect with ageing under discharge in a fresh ozoniser A, at 2.67 kV (25°).

Time.	i_b .	i_L .	Δi .	% Δi .	Time.	i_b .	i_L .	Δi .	% Δi
0 min.	11.4	7.1	4.3	37.7	195 min.	13.4	7.7	5.7	42.5
15	11.4	7.1	4.3	37.7	210	13.4	7.7	5.7	42.5
30	13.0	8.7	4.3	33.1	225	13.4	7.7	5.7	42.5
45	14.0	8.9	5.1	36.4	240	13.6	7.7	5.9	43.1
60	12.6	7.7	4.9	38.9	255	13.8	7.7	6.1	44.2
75	12.8	7.4	5.4	42.2	270	13.8	7.7	6.1	44.2
90	12.6	7.4	5.2	42.3	285	13.8	7.7	6.1	44.2
105	13.0	7.7	5.3	40.8	300	14.1	8.1	6.0	43.5
120	13.0	7.7	5.3	40.8	315	16.1	9.7	6.4	40.0
135	13.0	7.4	5.6	43.1	330	16.1	9.7	6.4	40.0
150	12.8	7.4	5.4	42.2	345	16.1	9.7	6.4	40.0
165	13.4	7.7	5.7	42.5	360	16.1	9.7	6.4	40.0
180	13.4	7.7	5.7	42.5					

TABLE II

Influence of exciting potential (kV) and light frequency on the Joshi-effect in ozoniser A, 'aged' under discharge.

kV.		White (7800-3700Å)	Blue (4750-4000Å)	Green (5775-5070Å)	Red (7070-6070Å)
1.34	i_D	—	2.2	2.2	2.2
	i_L	—	2.2	2.2	2.2
1.6	i_D	5.0	5.0	5.5	5.5
	i_L	1.6	2.5	3.3	4.4
	Δi	3.4	2.5	2.2	1.1
	% Δi	67.0	50.0	40.0	20.0
1.87	i_D	8.0	8.1	8.7	8.1
	i_L	2.3	3.6	4.5	6.3
	Δi	5.7	4.5	4.2	1.8
	% Δi	71.0	55.0	48.0	22.2
2.14	i_D	10.8	10.9	11.4	11.6
	i_L	3.0	4.5	5.9	8.9
	Δi	7.8	6.4	5.5	2.7
	% Δi	72.8	58.7	48.2	23.0
2.4	i_D	12.8	13.2	14.7	14.5
	i_L	4.9	5.5	8.7	11.8
	Δi	8.1	7.7	6.0	2.7
	% Δi	62.8	58.3	49.8	18.6
2.67	i_D	16.1	16.7	18.3	18.2
	i_L	6.3	8.1	11.6	15.3
	Δi	9.8	8.6	6.7	2.9
	% Δi	60.9	51.5	36.8	15.8
2.94	i_D	20.2	21.2	23.9	23.9
	i_L	10.2	11.4	16.9	21.2
	Δi	10.0	9.8	7.0	2.7
	% Δi	49.4	46.2	29.2	11.2
3.21	i_D	25.6	26.5	29.6	29.7
	i_L	15.5	16.6	22.9	27.4
	Δi	10.1	9.9	6.7	2.3
	% Δi	39.3	37.4	20.5	7.9
3.47	i_D	31.2	31.5	35.6	31.8
	i_L	21.1	21.6	29.1	32.6
	Δi	10.1	10.0	6.6	2.2
	% Δi	32.3	31.6	18.5	6.3
3.74	i_D	37.5	37.9	40.3	41.5
	i_L	27.0	27.4	33.7	39.2
	Δi	10.5	10.5	6.6	2.3
	% Δi	28.0	27.7	16.3	5.5
4.01	i_D	45.0	45.2	47.2	47.9
	i_L	33.2	33.6	40.4	45.7
	Δi	11.8	11.6	6.8	2.2
	% Δi	26.0	25.6	14.1	4.5

TABLE III

Influence of light frequency on the Joshi effect during ageing of a further 'aged' ozoniser A.

Time.	i_D .	i_W .	i_N .	i_a .	i_n .	Δi_w .	Δi_D .	Δi_a .	Δi_n .	% Δi_w .	% Δi_D .	% Δi_a .	% Δi_n .
0 min.	32.2	27.2	29.8	29.8	30.2	5.0	2.4	2.4	1.0	15.5	7.4	7.4	3.1
15	29.1	24.3	25.3	25.7	27.7	4.8	3.8	3.4	1.4	16.5	13.0	11.4	4.8
30	30.0	25.0	27.7	27.9	29.5	5.0	2.3	2.1	0.5	16.7	7.6	7.0	1.6
45	31.3	26.1	28.5	28.8	30.0	5.2	2.8	2.5	1.3	16.6	8.9	8.0	4.1
60	35.7	28.5	30.7	31.5	32.7	7.2	5.0	4.2	3.0	20.1	14.0	11.7	8.4
75	34.5	27.9	30.7	31.0	32.1	6.6	3.8	3.5	2.4	19.1	11.0	10.1	7.0
90	37.3	31.1	33.3	33.8	36.5	6.2	4.0	3.5	0.8	16.9	10.7	9.4	2.1
105	37.1	29.1	30.5	31.0	34.9	8.0	6.6	6.1	2.2	21.5	18.0	16.4	6.0
120	41.8	33.3	33.8	34.5	38.5	8.5	8.0	7.3	3.3	20.3	19.1	17.4	7.9
135	41.9	34.4	37.1	37.9	39.9	7.5	4.8	4.0	2.0	17.9	11.4	9.5	4.7
150	41.0	34.1	35.1	37.1	39.4	6.9	4.9	3.9	1.6	16.9	11.9	9.3	3.9
165	42.5	35.6	37.9	38.3	40.6	6.9	4.6	4.2	1.9	16.2	10.8	9.8	4.2
180	41.6	34.9	37.3	38.5	38.9	6.7	4.3	3.1	2.7	16.1	10.3	9.4	6.4
195	43.1	35.2	38.5	38.7	39.4	7.9	4.6	4.4	3.7	18.3	10.7	10.2	8.5
210	40.9	32.7	34.9	35.4	37.4	8.2	6.0	5.5	3.5	20.0	14.6	13.4	8.5
225	42.7	34.8	36.6	37.8	38.5	7.9	6.1	4.9	4.2	18.5	14.3	11.4	9.8
240	42.2	35.1	35.9	36.5	37.8	7.1	6.3	5.7	4.4	16.8	14.9	13.5	10.4
255	41.3	34.5	36.6	38.5	38.5	6.8	4.7	2.8	2.8	16.4	11.9	6.6	6.6
270	42.2	34.8	37.0	37.9	40.1	7.4	5.3	4.3	2.1	17.5	12.3	10.1	5.0
285	41.0	33.8	36.1	36.9	37.6	7.2	4.9	4.1	3.4	17.5	11.9	10.0	8.2
300	41.3	34.9	36.6	37.1	37.7	6.4	4.7	4.2	3.6	15.4	11.3	10.1	8.7
315	39.9	33.9	35.4	36.9	37.0	6.9	4.5	3.0	2.9	17.2	11.2	7.5	7.2
330	41.0	35.8	36.1	36.9	37.6	7.2	4.9	4.1	3.4	17.5	11.9	10.0	8.7
345	41.0	33.8	36.1	36.9	37.6	7.2	4.9	4.1	3.4	17.5	11.9	10.0	8.7
360	41.0	33.8	36.1	36.9	37.6	7.2	4.9	4.1	3.4	17.5	11.9	10.0	8.7
375	41.0	33.8	36.1	36.9	37.6	7.2	4.9	4.1	3.4	17.5	11.9	10.0	8.7

TABLE IV

Comparative influence of temperature and exciting potential (kV) on the Joshi effect in a long 'aged' ozoniser A, and fresh one, B

kV.	Ozoniser A.								Ozoniser B.				
	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°	65°	70°	80°	25°	50°	60°	65°	
1.34	i_D	—	—	—	—	11.8	12.0	12.6	10.9	—	—	—	
	i_L	—	—	—	—	10.2	10.1	10.5	10.7	—	—	—	
	Δi	—	—	—	—	1.6	1.9	2.1	0.2	—	—	—	
	% Δi	—	—	—	—	13.5	16.0	16.6	1.8	—	—	—	
1.60	i_D	14.8	16.0	16.2	16.6	17.2	19.2	23.0	23.7	16.4	20.7	23.2	22.1
	i_L	13.4	14.4	14.3	14.5	14.6	14.0	15.2	15.5	14.7	16.6	16.6	15.2
	Δi	1.4	1.6	1.9	2.1	2.6	5.2	7.8	8.2	1.7	4.1	6.6	6.9
	% Δi	9.4	10.0	11.6	12.6	15.1	27.0	33.6	34.6	10.3	19.8	28.4	31.2
1.87	i_D	21.0	22.4	22.9	23.7	25.7	29.1	34.5	37.7	23.9	34.8	37.0	36.0
	i_L	17.9	19.0	19.2	19.5	20.5	19.4	22.1	22.0	19.9	25.9	24.3	22.1
	Δi	3.1	3.4	3.7	4.2	4.9	9.7	12.4	15.7	4.0	8.9	12.7	13.9
	% Δi	14.9	15.1	16.1	17.7	19.2	33.3	35.9	41.6	16.7	25.5	34.3	38.6
2.14	i_D	26.4	30.9	31.8	31.8	34.3	39.4	46.6	51.1	31.3	47.7	51.0	48.9
	i_L	21.9	25.2	25.9	25.5	27.0	25.8	30.2	30.5	25.3	37.4	37.0	32.4
	Δi	4.5	5.7	5.9	6.3	7.3	13.6	16.4	20.6	6.0	10.3	14.0	16.5
	% Δi	17.0	18.4	18.5	19.8	21.2	34.5	35.2	40.3	19.1	21.5	27.4	33.7
2.40	i_D	37.4	41.9	39.1	40.1	43.1	50.5	59.4	66.4	40.6	60.4	64.1	62.1
	i_L	30.3	33.8	31.6	31.6	33.8	33.5	39.5	42.7	32.1	49.8	50.3	42.8
	Δi	7.1	8.1	7.5	8.5	9.3	17.0	19.0	23.7	8.5	10.6	13.8	19.3
	% Δi	19.0	19.3	19.1	21.2	21.5	33.6	33.5	35.6	20.9	17.5	21.5	31.0
2.67	i_D	48.1	52.5	49.8	52.4	54.9	62.8	74.6	83.1	49.1	71.2	80.3	70.6
	i_L	38.5	42.5	40.0	41.9	44.0	41.9	52.2	56.2	38.7	60.0	64.5	51.0
	Δi	9.6	10.0	9.8	10.5	10.9	20.9	22.4	26.9	40.4	11.2	15.5	19.6
	% Δi	19.9	19.0	19.6	20.0	19.8	33.2	30.0	32.3	21.1	15.7	19.6	27.7
2.94	i_D	61.6	65.7	62.1	65.4	68.6	79.3	—	—	63.6	—	—	—
	i_L	50.8	54.6	50.9	53.5	56.7	55.0	—	—	51.7	—	—	—
	Δi	10.8	11.1	11.2	11.9	11.9	24.3	—	—	11.9	—	—	—
	% Δi	17.0	17.5	18.0	18.1	17.3	30.6	—	—	18.7	—	—	—

DISCUSSION

The foregoing results given in Tables I-IV show that the Joshi effect corresponding to a photo-dimination of current in the range 2 to 73 % occurs in high pressure chlorine as used in the present work ; the effect increases in the order : red < green < blue < unfiltered white. This order is to be expected from general photochemical considerations. The results also show that the relative effect, viz.,

$$\frac{100 \times \Delta i}{i_D} = \% \Delta i,$$

where i_D is the current in dark, increases by increasing the applied potential (kV), and

reaches a maximum near 2.1 kV. The 'threshold potential' (Joshi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22 A, 225) characterised by a sudden increase of i at V , and termed V_m , and near which the system breaks down as a dielectric, lay near 1.6 kV and was affected by temperature and what is more, by 'ageing' under discharge (*vide infra*). These results support Joshi's discrimination of 'threshold potential' from the Paschen or spark potential (*Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548; 1946, 15, 281, 282).

The results in Table I, with ozoniser A, show that the current, i_n , at 2.7 kV tends to increase by nearly 40% after about 6 hours of ageing; any additional exposure produces but a small increase in i_n . The above remark applies also to the current under light, i_L . It is interesting that both the net Joshi effect, $\Delta i = i_n - i_L$, and the relative effect, $\% \Delta i$, reach maximum at the above stage, and remain practically stationary thereafter. The above deduction holds for irradiations in various filtered bands as also the unfiltered white. The time variation in conductivity under fairly constant electrical conditions is attributable to a progress of chemical reaction between the excited gas and the walls of the ozoniser. Due to continued discharge as under 'ageing', a rise of temperature of about 15° to 25° occurred in the system. This should favour an increased chemical action, as also the circumstances that the gas pressure now used is much greater than that employed by previous workers in this line, a deduction in accord with Joshi's finding that the law of mass action may be applied to an appreciable extent to the chemical action produced under an electrical discharge (*Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 175).

Table II records the results of the influence of light frequency (mean) on the effect, Δi . The current in dark, i_n and under irradiation, i_L , in the various wave bands used, increase progressively with the applied potential. The variation of i_L in the different frequency regions at a given applied potential is in the order: red > green > blue > unfiltered white, and hence Δi , i.e., ($i_n - i_L$) varies in the opposite sense in respect of the frequency of light. It is interesting to note that the difference in respect of i_L in white and in blue light decreases with the exciting potential (kV), whereas the difference between blue and green or green and red increases with the exciting potential. Thus, e.g., the differences in the values of i_L between white and blue, blue and green, and green and red, are 1.8, 3.5 and 3.7 respectively at applied potential 2.67 kV, and 0.4, 7.4 and 6.4 respectively at 3.47 kV. It was also observed that the effect, Δi , under white (unfiltered) light was less than the additive effect due to the filtered components, viz., blue, green, and red. This difference in respect of $\% \Delta i$ decreases with increase of the exciting potential; thus e.g., it decreases from 57.1 to 18.5 when the corresponding applied potential is increased from 2.14 to 4.01 kV. It follows from the above results that the light frequency is the main factor in the production of the above phenomenon. It is, however, interesting to see that the effect under white and blue is much more pronounced than that due to green and red. This may be associated with the circumstance that both the former regions include appreciably the main absorption band of chlorine, viz., 2300-5000 Å (Joshi, *loc. cit.*).

It may be mentioned here that when the experiments referred to above were completed, the ozoniser A had been exposed to the discharge for a period of 30 hours. The Joshi effect, Δi , was then observed in the various light bands, during a further continuous 'ageing', i.e., exposure to discharge for about 6 hours (*vide Table III*).

These results show that the current in dark, i_0 , and the current under irradiation by white (unfiltered) light (i_w), blue light (i_b), green light (i_g), and red light (i_r), increase with time. The current i_0 rises to a maximum in about 2 hours after which time it remains practically constant. Thus at the end of 2, 4 and 6 hours, the increase in i_0 is 30%, 31% and 27% respectively. This remark also applies to the current under light in the above mentioned regions. The effect, Δi_{White} , Δi_{Blue} , Δi_{Green} , Δi_{Red} increases with time of exposure up to about 5 hours and remains practically constant thereafter. It is, however, interesting to note that this influence of ageing leading to the enhancement of the effect Δi , follows the order: red > green > blue > white. Thus, e.g., the increase of Δi_{White} at the end of 2, 4 and 6 hours is 70%, 42% and 44% respectively, whereas the corresponding increase of Δi_{Red} is 230%, 340% and 240% respectively.

An examination of the data in Table IV shows that i_0 , i_r , and Δi increase progressively with the exciting potential (kV). With increase of temperature the 'threshold potential', V_m , however, decreases, e.g., V_m changes from 1.6 to 1.3 kV when the corresponding temperature is raised from 25° to 65°. At constant exciting potential (kV), i_0 , Δi and % Δi increase with temperature. Thus, e.g., at 2.14 kV, i_0 in dark increases from 26.4 at 25° to 51.1 at 80°. The net effect Δi and % Δi are respectively 4.5 and 17 at 25° and 19 and 38.1 at 80°. When the ozoniser was cooled from 80° to 25°, the effect Δi and % Δi were found to have undergone a permanent increase, compared with the corresponding values at this temperature, observed before heating the system. This deduction is borne out by the results in Table IV for the second ozoniser B, also filled with high pressure chlorine. This ozoniser B was, however, fresh, i.e., 'unaged' under discharge.

Joshi has emphasised the significance of the 'threshold potential' V_m , for discharge reactions in general and the effect Δi in particular (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 120; *Nature*, 1945, 154, 147). He has shown that the current i depends upon $V - V_m$ (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 389), and that Δi tends to increase with i over a certain limit. From the results in Table IV it is seen that $V - V_m$ increases, since V_m diminishes with temperature (*vide supra*), and hence the current i_0 and the effect Δi increase. The change in Δi may also be attributed to the change in the wall surface at higher temperature. Chlorine is a reactive gas and much more so under electrical fields. Aided by high temperature and electric fields chlorine should react chemically with the wall material. These results in Table IV, showing an increase of Δi with temperature, are at variance with those of Deo and co-workers (*loc. cit.*), observed with much smaller gas pressure, viz., 148 mm. In Joshi's theory for the effect Δi , an electrode or a boundary layer, derived in part from the adsorption of ions and molecules of the excited gas, plays an important part. The extent of such interaction of the gas should be less at low gas pressure than at the large ones now used. It has been shown by Joshi that within limits, the pressure of the gas is a chief determinant of the magnitude of the effect. When the initial pressure of the gas under discharge is high, and when the system is heated, the pressure of the gas under discharge is high, and when the system is heated, the pressure will increase favouring an increase in Δi , and the further increase of pressure, which would ordinarily be inhibitory towards the effect, is removed by wall action leading to the formation of an adsorption layer of NaCl.

Under the conditions of the present experiment, there are two opposite tendencies at the higher temperature, one to decrease the effect due to the deranging of the boundary layer, and the other to increase the effect due to chemical action by some partial reduction of the extra gas pressure as mentioned above. The effect due to the enhanced interaction of the excited gas with the glass walls of the ozoniser would appear to be greater than that of (partial) destruction of the electrode layer due to heating. This view is in accord with the significant observation, mentioned above, viz., the effect at a given temperature is comparatively large when the gas is aged at higher temperature.

It is instructive to consider the observed increase of i with ageing under discharge and especially that due to pre-heating. Joshi has shown that the current in an ozoniser system is given by the following equation:—

$$i = \frac{V}{\frac{i}{jC_w \sum f} + \frac{i}{R_g} + jC_g \sum f} \quad \dots (1)$$

where C_w is the combined capacity due to inner and outer annular walls and C_g is the capacity of the gas in the annular space; $\sum f$ represents not only the frequency of A.C. supply and its harmonics, but also those produced under electric discharge due to V (*Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19). According to this equation, i should increase by an increase in any one or more of the quantities, i/R_g , C_g , C_w and $\sum f$. The ohmic current i/R_g is a function of the number of ions per c.c. and their average velocity; these should not change sensibly with temperature *per se*. Since C_g is measured by the dielectric constant of the gas, which decreases with temperature, a change therein, due to heating cannot explain the observed rise of i by ageing. The dielectric constant of glass increases by 0.2% per degree rise in temperature and therefore on that account C_w might increase by about 11% over the operative temperature change adopted in this work. The corresponding rise in i , expected from equation (1), is, however, but a small part of the rise in i due to heating, viz., 100%

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